

MUSIC CULTURE IN THE AGE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article discusses the musical culture and its theoretical importance in today's rapidly developing era. recommendations are also made on the integration of music education with technology.

Keywords: music culture, digital technologies, music education, music web applications.

It should be noted that, in comparison with a number of economically developed countries, the ability of Uzbekistan to create an original musical product is not yet at a sufficiently high level, and the corresponding legal system is far from perfect. The process of training professional personnel also needs to be improved. All this has become problems limiting the development of the musical cultural industry in Uzbekistan.

The music culture industry refers to a range of activities related to the production, distribution, service and consumption of music content. The most important link in the entire production chain is the provision of high-quality musical products, the key elements of which are creative, copyright and other intangible capital.

It should be noted that in order to create and further promote, the product of the music industry must have the following characteristics:

- ❖ *the presence of an idea, creativity:*
- ❖ *possession of the necessary theoretical and practical competencies:*
- ❖ *understanding that a cultural musical product has a quality of high added value:*
- ❖ *associated with the economy and actually incorporated into its sphere.*

Modern musical creativity today must meet the criterion of originality, and the creators of a cultural product must pay attention to the most diverse nuances of its creation and sale. This means that the author / authors of the work need to build relationships, communicate with designers, stylists, producers, promoters, etc. A modern product is no longer the result of the creativity of only one person - rather, it is the fruit (co-)authorship of many people. Of considerable importance is the ability to overcome the limitations of the traditional framework of thinking, which initiates the ability to create new ideas, requires inspiration, creative imagination. The production of high-quality musical products requires deep theoretical knowledge. The style, technique and

expressiveness of the work reflect the theoretical knowledge of the author, his cultural philosophy and worldview.

The music cultural industry is, to a large extent, a highly developed digital sphere, closely connected or even included in the economy. Therefore, it must have a high level of technical development, especially as the digital music platform becomes more and more advanced. This involves the formation of a diverse musical environment, its content of high quality in terms of technical accessibility, as well as the provision of such a product that makes the user desire and willingness to pay. Obviously, the cost of high-quality technical equipment, recording, use, promotion of the product significantly increases its value. This feature, as well as the value-spiritual content of musical works, must be taken into account when they are produced and put on the market. The connection of the music industry products with the economy is manifested not only in the context of its characteristics as a commodity, but also in the form of inclusion in other areas of the cultural industries - tourism, sports, and also in the field of education. The new development of the industry is manifested in a complex system in which upstream and downstream interact with each other, and each element of communication supports each other.

Along with the development of the musical and cultural industry in Uzbekistan, there are certain problems. In this digital age, the development of the music culture industry can not only improve people's cultural needs and artistic achievements, but also expand consumption, increase employment opportunities, and stabilize economic growth. Therefore, the further development of the musical culture industry and the solution of socio-cultural and economic problems in Uzbekistan should be considered a priority. The level of musical education determines the quality of musical personnel, and the activities of various musical institutions in the field of education and training should, in our opinion, be improved. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce national and world relevant experience, innovative forms and methods of training into the personnel training system. This thesis applies not only to the training of performers, musicians, but also promoters, managers, marketers specializing in the field of cultural industries. In addition, cultural education departments at all levels of the education system should integrate music education resources and provide comprehensive support for musical talents. The music industry still needs to standardize legislation. This applies primarily to such a phenomenon as music piracy. We believe that it is necessary to increase fines for violating the rights to video and musical works, to increase the

amount of compensation for damage caused to authors. In general, the copyright protection system should work more efficiently. This will provide strong legal protection for most music copyright holders.

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